

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Today digital assistants have become not only a universally recognized area of computer language learning — CALL (computer-assisted language learning), but also an important part of teaching English in general. Computer quest games that appeared several decades ago representing problem tasks, activating cognitive activities as well and increasing students' motivation are of great importance. With the development of the Internet speed and affordable storage costs such segments as online games appeared. Online games allow us to present and master difficult material to any modern gadget in the form of a game. The article demonstrates the effectiveness of the use of interactive methods in foreign language teaching. The main types of educational quests in terms of their general classification and structure are identified. Based on English phrasal verbs, phraseological units, and logic puzzles the article proves that quest game is an innovative method of language teaching.

Keywords: English language, CALL, quest game.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, much attention is paid to the issues of increasing motivation and preserving and developing students' interest in a foreign language. A modern teacher is faced with the task of creating favorable conditions for language learning, choosing teaching methods that would allow everyone to identify the sphere of interest, and motivation and show imagination and creativity. In this case, the teacher acts as the initiator of the cognitive activity process and forms a personalized concept of learning a foreign language.

The introduction of new information technologies attracts an increasing number of supporters of digitalization. Today, teachers use interactive game methods, for example, quests as one of the most effective ways to learn a language, while simultaneously developing a new type of thinking inherent in the XXI century in students. Thus, interactive methods represent not only modern technical means but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process.

Interactive technology in the educational process as a concept appeared relatively recently. A big role in this was played by computer games of the Quest genre, the main idea of which was to find solutions to logical problems by interacting with the surrounding virtual environment.

The word quest means "search, the object of the search, the search for adventures", which in folklore works represents the journey of characters to a certain goal through logical decision chains and overcoming numerous obstacles. As a rule, the heroes during their wanderings met various characters who either helped them or hindered them (the Exploits of

Hercules, the Myth of Perseus, etc.). Modern educational quests are aimed at studying certain grammatical and lexical topics playfully.

The founders of the educational quests are Bernie Dodge, professor of educational technology at the University of San Diego (USA), and his student Tom March, an English teacher at the Poway School in California. Scientists have introduced the definition of a web quest — "a research activity in which some or all of the information that students interact with comes from resources on the Internet".

Since 1995, Dodge and March have been structuring a new type of educational activity, along with the development of key attributes of Web Quest, as one of the strategies for the successful integration of Internet resources into the educational process. The goal of the developers was to develop critical thinking skills, motivate students, and excitement in the competition game. It is the process of the game, whether it is a computer or real life, that has become the starting point that has become very popular in pedagogy. Since Bernie Dodge developed his model in 1995, many teachers have contributed to both the theory and practice of web quests.

Bernie Dodge has created innovative Internet applications for integration into the educational process when teaching various academic subjects at different levels of study. He defined "the quest" as a site containing a problematic task and involving an independent search for information on the Internet. He identified three principles of classification of web quests.

1. By duration of achievement.
2. By subject content.
3. By the type of tasks performed by the participants.

The skill set for creating a web quest can be defined as follows:

- research skills;
- analytical skills;
- production skills.

Today, the structure of web quests has undergone changes and is being developed in accordance with the needs and learning styles of a specific target group. Quests can be used at different levels of learning in the learning process. They can cover a separate topic, the entire academic subject, or they can be interdisciplinary. The advantage of quest lessons is the use of active teaching methods. It can be designed for both group and individual work.

According to the general classification, the following types of training quests are distinguished:

- linear — solving one problem makes it possible to solve the following;
- brainstorm — with the help of control prompts, the participant chooses the way to solve the problem himself;
- ring — the same linear quest only for several teams starting from different points.

According to the structure, educational quests are classified into:

- sequential quests — in which a puzzle is proposed step by step, after solving which participants receive a hint for passing the next stage;
- quests-projects — allow students to organize research activities in a playful way;
- quests-adventure are games in which you need not only to pass the next stage but also to collect hints that may be useful for completing tasks.

Interactive learning is valuable because each student is an active participant in the game, namely, the process of cognition. Interactive methodology allows you to make the learning process active for both the teacher and the student. It is impossible for one participant of the educational process to dominate over another. It is quests that today represent an interactive dynamic game with a large number of fascinating problem tasks, logical puzzles and tests, in which there are elements of risk and the spirit of competition.

Of course, the quest technology is designed not only to improve the perception of educational material. In the game, you need to be resourceful, train your own memory and attentiveness, show ingenuity. Quests help students to establish successful interaction in a team, form mutual assistance, division of responsibilities and interchangeability. Often the plots of quests echo the plots of popular films and books, so that participants, as a rule, it is not difficult to plunge into the necessary atmosphere. Starting from game lessons and ending with virtual tours around the world, today there are many interesting technical tools that can be used when learning languages. Introducing these innovations into the curriculum will not only help students master English but will increase their motivation to study.

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